

**Effect of alumina or zirconia particles on the performance of lead-free BCZT
piezoceramics**

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Abstract

The barium titanate derivative $\text{Ba}_{0.85}\text{Ca}_{0.15}\text{Zr}_{0.1}\text{Ti}_{0.9}\text{O}_3$ (BCZT) offers high dielectric and piezoelectric performance but has poor mechanical properties. Particle composites combining BCZT with tougher Al_2O_3 or ZrO_2 could be the solution to the inherent brittleness of electroceramics. This work focuses on BCZT with 1–5 vol.% of reinforcing phase dispersed in the microstructure. While hardness was improved in all composites, especially in ZrO_2 -reinforced BCZT, toughness was positively affected only by Al_2O_3 . The chemical reactivity of BCZT during sintering resulted in the formation of new barium aluminate phases at the grain boundaries and possibly also within the grains, which affected the electrical properties of the composites. The addition of zirconia resulted in the formation of BaZrO_3 or $\text{Ba}(\text{Zr},\text{Ti})\text{O}_3$, which is a natural part of the BCZT solid solution and shifts the phase composition towards relaxor behaviour. ZrO_2 -reinforced composites exhibited higher permittivity but lower ferroelectric properties, accompanied by a substantial Curie temperature decrease.

Keywords

Lead-free piezoceramics; Particle composite; Barium calcium zirconium titanate; Alumina; Zirconia

1. Introduction

In recent times, there has been a significant increase in the use of composites made from ferroelectric polymers and ceramics in various applications such as underwater hydrophones, ultrasound biomedical imaging, non-destructive testing, or smoke detector buzzers to novel applications in sporting goods and active and passive damping systems for automobile and aerospace sectors [1,2]. The ceramic fillers commonly used in these composites are often ferroelectrics with a high dielectric constant, compared to polymers, including calcium or samarium and magnesium-modified lead titanium [3–6], lead zirconate titanate [7], PMN-PT [8], and barium titanate (BT) [9]. Out of these fillers, BT is a widely utilised piezoelectric material known for its excellent dielectric and electromechanical properties. Moreover, it is environmentally friendly as it is lead-free, which is advantageous from an environmental protection perspective. At its Curie temperature, T_C (120 °C), the dielectric constant of BT surpasses 10000. However, as the temperature decreases from T_C to room temperature, the dielectric constant sharply drops due to the transition of BT from its cubic to tetragonal phase [10].

Recent research in the field of lead-free materials has been focused on modified BT-based ceramics, specifically addressing the phase transition temperature of BT ceramics. This can be achieved through A-site or B-site substitutions, such as the addition of calcium into the A-site (barium, Ba^{2+}) and zirconium into the B-site (titanium, Ti^{4+}) [11]. One such solid-solution, $Ba_{0.85}Ca_{0.15}Zr_{0.1}Ti_{0.9}O_3$ (hereafter BCZT), composed of $Ba(Zr_{0.2}Ti_{0.8})O_3$ and $(Ba_{0.7}Ca_{0.3})TiO_3$, has gained significant attention as an environmentally-friendly material [12]. Additionally, BCZT exhibits a notable piezoelectric performance comparable to

lead-based ceramics, making it a potential substitute for lead-based materials in various applications [13,14].

While the electrical properties of BCZT are important, the mechanical properties are equally crucial for its applications. Previous studies have explored the reinforcement of oxide (Al_2O_3 , MgO, ZrO_2 , and stabilized- ZrO_2) or non-oxide (SiC) particles, as well as metal particles, to improve the mechanical properties of structural ceramics and ferroelectrics [15–17]. It is well known that the electrical properties of ferroelectric ceramics tend to degrade with non-ferroelectric additives, and the sinterability decreases with refractory oxide additives. However, using nano-oxide additives may reduce the amount of additive required and minimise the degradation of electrical properties. Tajima et al. [18] demonstrated that the fracture toughness of PZT-based nanocomposites can be increased (1.7 times higher than standard PZT ceramics) with the addition of various oxides (Al_2O_3 , MgO, and ZrO_2).

Jiansirisomboon et al. [19] studied the effect of alumina nano powders on the electrical and mechanical properties of barium titanate ceramics. They found that the Knoop hardness and Young's modulus of BaTiO_3 were slightly improved with adding 0.5 vol.% of Al_2O_3 , while the piezoelectric coefficient and dielectric permittivity remained at a similar value to that of pure BaTiO_3 .

To the best of our knowledge, there are a couple of reports available on the study of mechanical properties of BCZT-based particle composites. Adhikari et al. [20] incorporated 1 vol.% nano-sized Al_2O_3 into the BCZT matrix, resulting in improved mechanical properties, with a 24% increase in flexural strength and a 29% increase in hardness. Furthermore, they maintained a good dielectric constant ($\epsilon_r = 3630$) and

piezoelectric properties ($d_{33} = 350$ pC/N) with a grain size ranging between approximately 4–7 μm . Due to the lower sintering temperature of 1300–1350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the BCZT matrix was the mixture of rhombohedral and tetragonal phases. Therefore, the dielectric permittivity is higher (4215 for pure BCZT). In addition, Yan et al. [21] demonstrated similar d_{33} ~ 320 pC/N with BCZT reinforced with 1 vol.% Al_2O_3 composite. However, the best mechanical properties such as Vickers hardness 6.26 GPa ($\sim 40\%$ increase as to pure BCZT) and fracture toughness of 1.06 $\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ together with a slight decrease in d_{33} ~ 160 pC/N were shown for BCZT with 4 vol.% Al_2O_3 composite. Another effect of Al_2O_3 inclusion is the reduction of conductivity, which is valuable profit for the capacitor dielectric. Yan et al. used two step sintering process (5 min at 1500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 4 h at 1350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and the resulting phase composition was tetragonal. Therefore, the dielectric permittivity was lower (about 2000 for pure BCZT).

This study aims to further explore the mechanical and electrical properties of BCZT composite material by incorporating ZrO_2 and Al_2O_3 nanoparticles into BCZT. By investigating the effects of these additives on the material properties, we hope to contribute to the development of lead-free materials with enhanced performance for various applications.

2. Experimental

2.1 Powder synthesis and consolidation

$\text{Ba}_{0.85}\text{Ca}_{0.15}\text{Zr}_{0.1}\text{Ti}_{0.9}\text{O}_3$ ceramics were synthesised by solid-state reaction. Used precursors BaCO_3 (Dakram, UK), CaCO_3 (Lachner, Czech Republic), TiO_2 (Dakram, UK), and ZrO_2 (Dakram, UK) were dried at 220 °C for 2 h and subsequently weighed according to stoichiometric ratios. The powder mixed with ethanol and zirconia milling balls was placed on a roller bench for 24 h. Then it was dried at 90 °C for 10 h, sieved (300 µm mesh), and finally calcined at 1250 °C for 4 h. Reinforcing phases added into synthesised BCZT powder were Al_2O_3 (A, TM-DAR Taimicron, Taimei Chemicals, Japan, particle size 120 nm) and tetragonal ZrO_2 (Z, TZ-3Y-E, Tosoh, Japan, particle size 60 nm) in concentrations of 1, 3, and 5 vol.%. Composites are hereafter denoted as A1, A3, A5 and Z1, Z3, Z5, respectively.

The calcined BCZT and composite powders were re-milled for another 24 h in ethanol, and 3 wt% of the binder polyethylene glycol ($M_n = 200$, Sigma Aldrich, USA) was added during the last hour of milling followed by drying at 90 °C for 10 h and sieving (300 µm mesh).

Powders were compacted into pellets with a diameter of 30 mm using the uniaxial press (BSML21, Brio Hranice, Czech Republic) at 15 MPa followed by cold isostatic pressing (KIP 300 E, P/O/Webber, Germany) at 300 MPa.

2.2 Heat treatment

Green bodies were annealed at 800 °C for 1 h to burn out the binder and subsequently sintered in the superkanthal high-temperature furnace (type 0517S, Clasic, Czech Republic) at 1520 °C in air with 2 h dwell and 10 °C/min heating and cooling rates.

2.3 Characterisation of the samples

The densities of green bodies and sintered samples were measured by the Archimedes method (EN 18754). The theoretical densities (TD) of BCZT, ZrO₂, and Al₂O₃ used for the calculations of relative densities were 5.74 g/cm³ (obtained from X-ray diffraction results), 6.05 g/cm³, and 3.99 g/cm³, respectively. The microstructure and chemical composition were studied using a Lyra scanning electron microscope (SEM, Tescan, Czech Republic) equipped with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy analyser (EDX, Oxford Instruments, United Kingdom) on fracture surfaces and polished (1 µm) cross-sections of the sintered bodies. The mean grain size (MGS) was measured using a linear intercept method. The results were multiplied by a correction factor of 1.56 [22]. The phase composition of the ceramics prepared was analysed by X-ray powder diffractometer SmartLab 3kW (XRD, Rigaku, Japan) using the Bragg-Brentano setup with Cu-K α radiation source ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$). The data analysis was performed using the Rietveld refinement method in PDXL software (Rigaku, Japan).

Elastic properties were determined on the sintered discs using the Impulse Excitation Technique (IET) on the RFDA Professional device (IMCE, Belgium) in accordance with the standard ASTM E1876. Young's elastic modulus E and shear modulus G were calculated from the respective resonance frequencies of flexural and torsional loading modes. The

Poisson ratio μ was calculated from the obtained values of the E and G moduli. At least 10 valid measurements for each material were conducted.

Vickers microhardness HV0.3 was measured using an instrumented hardness head ZHU02 installed on a universal testing machine Z2.5 (Zwick/Roel, Germany). The measurement was conducted on the polished cross-sections embedded in the epoxy resin according to EN 14705. The applied maximal indentation force was 2.98 N with a loading speed of 0.3725 N/s and held at the maximum load of 12 s. The indentation elastic modulus was calculated from the unloading branch of the loading curve. A minimum of 20 indents were used to calculate an average value for each material.

The fracture resistance of all materials was determined using a standardised chevron notch technique (ASTM C1421). The bending bars ($3.5 \times 2.5 \times 20$ mm) were cut from the discs and ground to obtain sufficient surface quality. Chevron notch was cut to the bars using a precious saw Isomet 5000 (Buehler, USA) equipped with an ultrathin diamond disc with a thickness of 0.15mm. The three-point bending configuration with a span of 16 mm was used for loading. A universal testing system 8862 (Instron, USA) was employed for loading at a crosshead speed of 0.005 mm/min ensuring a valid crack propagation. The slice model was used to calculate the geometrical function, as shown elsewhere [23,24]. The fracture toughness values were calculated using the geometry of the specimen and setup, a calculated minimum of geometrical function and the maximum reached force. At least 20 valid fracture toughness values per material were evaluated and using a normal distribution statistically characterised. The mean values and corresponding scatters are reported.

Prior to poling, silver (Ag) paste was applied on the samples followed by firing at 700 °C for 10 min. The quasistatic piezoelectric constant, d_{33} (pC/N), was measured by Berlincourt d_{33} meter (ZJ-3C, Institute of physics, China) after poling in silicon oil at 3 kV/mm for 10 min (at room temperature). A small signal converse piezoelectric constants (sine wave function; 50 V; 1 kHz) were calculated by a piezoelectric evaluation system (aixPES, aixACCT systems, Germany) on sintered samples. The ferroelectric properties were evaluated by sine wave function of electric field amplitude 3 kV/mm and frequency 1 Hz. The dependence of relative permittivity on temperature was measured by a precision impedance analyser (4294A, Agilent, USA) where sine wave function with amplitude 1 V and frequency 1 kHz was used. The measurement was performed on poled samples in temperature range 30 °C up to 120 °C with step 2 °C. The Curie temperature was evaluated from these measurements as the temperature where the highest relative permittivity was observed.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Powder characterisation

The calcined BCZT powder was thoroughly analysed to determine its phase structure, particle size, and morphology. Fig. 1a shows the XRD pattern of BCZT powder with sharp and distinct peaks, indicating good crystallinity of the material. The most intense peaks are attributed to perovskite BCZT. However, the low intensity peaks (marked by triangles and diamonds) suggest the existence of BaZrO_3 and CaTiO_3 phases because of an incompleting solid-state reaction. These phases occur relatively commonly during the same type of powder preparation even after calcination [25,26]. Secondary phases usually disappear at the sintering stage, leaving only the desired perovskite phase in the microstructure [26].

The particle distribution of the BCZT powder is given in Fig. 1b. The calcined powder had a unimodal distribution with $d_{50} = 4.9 \mu\text{m}$. The micrograph in Fig. 1c shows that BCZT powder was mainly composed of aggregated particles. The primary particles had their size in the range of 1–3 μm having a polyhedral shape due to the high calcination temperature. Such a morphology of ceramic powder is not very favourable for its shaping and densification. Therefore, the pressure-assisted shaping methods were applied for the preparation of green bodies.

Fig. 1 XRD pattern (a), particle size distribution (b), and SEM micrograph (c) of calcined BCZT.

3.2 Phase composition of BCZT and BCZT-based particle composites

Fig. 2 shows XRD patterns of sintered BCZT and BCZT-based particle composites. The pure BCZT ceramics exhibited a pure perovskite structure without secondary phases within the detectable limit of the XRD, indicating a completed solid-state reaction. However, the minority secondary phases were detected when incorporating zirconia or alumina reinforcing ceramics. Adding zirconia resulted in the presence of tetragonal ZrO_2 (#ICSD 157620) and $\text{Ba}_6\text{Ti}_{17}\text{O}_{40}$ (#ICSD 014299), as evident in detail at 2θ in the range of $24\text{--}32^\circ$ in Fig. 2b. Ti-rich phase $\text{Ba}_6\text{Ti}_{17}\text{O}_{40}$ has been reported after adding ZrO_2 to BaTiO_3 , a similar system to BCZT; Zr^{4+} was incorporated into the *B*-site of the BaTiO_3 lattice and released excessive TiO_2 , which reacted with BaTiO_3 and formed $\text{Ba}_6\text{Ti}_{17}\text{O}_{40}$ [27]. The formation of this phase also necessitates a second reaction product of BaZrO_3 , or solid solution $\text{Ba}(\text{Ti},\text{Zr})\text{O}_3$ [27]. Especially, the excess formation of $\text{Ba}(\text{Zr}_{0.2}\text{Ti}_{0.8})\text{O}_3$ compound (building element of

BCT-BZT solid solution resulting in superior BCZT system) may further contribute to final phase composition of BCZT ceramics shifted towards the relaxor behaviour (i.e., Zr-rich composition).

In case of BCZT reinforced by alumina, secondary phases BaAl_2O_4 (#ICSD 015728) and $\text{Ba}_4\text{Ti}_{10}\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{27}$ (#ICSD 087085) were detected (see Fig. 2e). Presence of BaAl_2O_4 and $\text{Ba}_4\text{Ti}_{10}\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{27}$ has been reported before in Al_2O_3 -reinforced BaTiO_3 , together with $\text{Ba}_6\text{Ti}_{17}\text{O}_{40}$ phase [28,29]. However, diffraction patterns of $\text{Ba}_4\text{Ti}_{10}\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{27}$ and $\text{Ba}_6\text{Ti}_{17}\text{O}_{40}$ overlap to a large extent and accurate phase attribution in current samples was difficult due to the small concentration of secondary phases. Among other secondary phases formed in BaTiO_3 reinforced by Al_2O_3 particles let us mention $\text{BaTiAl}_6\text{O}_{12}$ and $\text{Ba}_3\text{TiAl}_{10}\text{O}_{20}$ [30].

The reflection angles of pure BCZT around $2\theta = 45^\circ$ correspond well to that of combined tetragonal (#ICSD 230567) and orthorhombic (#ICSD 230568) symmetry and similar results have been reported before [31–35]. Considering the intensities of the examined peaks, the tetragonal phase was dominant, having a c/a ratio of 1.0043.

The samples reinforced with zirconia show a shift to diffraction peaks of (022) and (200), indicating the increase of the orthorhombic phase resulting in the c/a ratio decrease of the remaining tetragonal phase, as summarised in Table 1. In the case of alumina-reinforced BCZT samples, the dominant tetragonal phase structure seemed stable up to the concentration of 3 vol.% followed by a sharp decrease of tetragonality (see Table 1) and an increased amount of orthorhombic phase.

Table 1 Summarised c/a ratios of BCZT reinforced with ZrO_2 and Al_2O_3 . Pure BCZT standard had $c/a = 1.0043$.

vol.%	c/a ratio ZrO_2 [-]	c/a ratio Al_2O_3 [-]
1	1.0019	1.0039
3	1.0012	1.0031
5	1.0012	1.0010

Increased volume of reinforcing ZrO_2 in the matrix resulted in the shift of the diffraction peaks to lower angles (see Fig. 2c). This was due to an enlargement of the crystal lattice as a consequence of the replacement of smaller Ti^{4+} ($r = 0.61 \text{ \AA}$) ions by a larger Zr^{4+} ($r = 0.72 \text{ \AA}$) ions [36] at B site. From this point of view, a more significant shift to a low angle for Zr^{4+} ion-containing lattice was expected [37]. The slight shift observed in Al_2O_3 -reinforced BCZT was probably connected to the gradual decrease of tetragonal phase content.

Fig. 2 X-ray diffraction patterns of sintered BCZT and BCZT reinforced by ZrO_2 (Z) or Al_2O_3 (A) ceramics and enlarged views of the peaks at $2\theta \approx 30^\circ$ and $2\theta \approx 45^\circ$.

3.3 Microstructural observation

The relative density of green bodies was around 62.5% of TD for all the compositions. The pure BCZT sample reached almost 95.0% of TD after sintering, which is comparable

with the same material densified in previous works using pressureless sintering at temperatures between 1450 and 1540 °C [31–33,38].

Fig. 3 Dependence of relative density and MGS on the concentration of reinforcing Al₂O₃ and ZrO₂ ceramics in BCZT matrix.

The dependence of sintered sample's relative density and MGS on the concentration of reinforcing ceramics is shown in Fig. 3. An addition of a small concentration of secondary phase into BCZT or BaTiO₃ (up to 1 vol.%) usually resulted in increased densification of the sample, but the higher amount of secondary phase was more likely to inhibit the sintering [19,20,39]. This behaviour is clearly visible in Fig. 3, where 1 vol.% of reinforcing alumina and/or zirconia ceramics resulted in the same or slightly higher relative density followed by a steep drop in density values.

Generally, the MGS of BCZT ceramics sintered at high temperatures around 1500 °C has been reported in the range of 14–40 μm [32,33,35,38–42]. Currently measured MGS value

of 32 μm for pure BCZT falls within this range. Increasing the concentration of ZrO_2 slightly refined the microstructure down to 27 μm . Al_2O_3 had a more profound effect on the grain size, which decreased to around 20 μm for all studied concentrations. It is obvious from Fig. 3 that the dependence of MGS on the reinforcing phase concentration does not follow the trend shown for the density. In general, a reinforcing phase could act as an obstacle to the motion of grain boundaries and thus retard grain growth [43]. However, XRD analysis showed a negligible amount of the original Al_2O_3 or ZrO_2 phases. Instead, complex secondary phases were recorded, see Fig. 2 **Error! Reference source not found.**

SEM micrographs of sintered samples' microstructures are shown in Fig. 4 and detailed inspection showed that secondary phases were located at the grain boundary of BCZT grains, resulting in the mentioned reduced grain boundary mobility during sintering. Overall micrographs show that regardless of the phase composition, microstructure contained large grains with a substantial amount of intergranular porosity. A similar state of the sintered BCZT ceramics microstructure has been reported before [31,44,45].

Fig. 4 SEM micrographs of BCZT and BCZT with added 1, 3, 5 vol.% of ZrO_2 or Al_2O_3 and detailed micrographs of composite microstructure reinforced with 3 vol.% ZrO_2 or Al_2O_3 with highlighted spots for EDX spectra acquisition (note different scale bars).

To evaluate the chemical nature of observed phases, the EDX analyses of BCZT samples reinforced with 3 vol.% ZrO_2 or Al_2O_3 were performed in selected spots displayed in detailed SEM micrographs in Fig. 4. Atomic concentrations of elements from spots 1 and 2 corresponded to pure BCZT. The secondary phases were analysed in spots 3 and 4 and were attributed to $\text{Ba}_6\text{Ti}_{17}\text{O}_{40}$ and $\text{Ba}_4\text{Ti}_{10}\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{27}$, respectively, although a low intensity signal for Zr element was present. We believe that in both cases, residual Zr was detected from the surrounding BCZT grains. The dark phase at spot 5 was Al, Ba, and O-rich and therefore corresponds to the BaAl_2O_4 phase.

Table 2 Atomic concentrations of elements from point EDX spectra indicated in Fig. 4

Spot (Sample)	Ba [at. %]	Ti [at. %]	O [at. %]	Ca [at. %]	Zr [at. %]	Al [at. %]
1 (Z3)	16.3	16.2	61.1	2.8	3.6	0.0
2 (A3)	17.3	18.8	58.6	2.9	2.3	0.1
3 (Z3)	8.7	23.1	65.6	0.9	1.7	0.0
4 (A3)	10.4	22.3	60.9	1.2	1.5	3.7
5 (A3)	7.0	3.6	73.4	0.6	0.2	15.2

3.4 Mechanical properties

Elastic properties of all prepared composites were determined from the discs via the resonance method and the results are plotted in Fig. 5a. Young's modulus and shear modulus for pure BCZT were around 83 and 30 GPa, respectively. These values correspond well with the literature data [46]. A slight increase in elastic properties was observed with an increasing amount of added alumina and a surprisingly stronger effect was found for zirconia addition. The maximum increase of 9% and 28% was obtained for 5 vol.% alumina and zirconia addition, respectively. An effect in the case of the alumina-reinforcing phase should be stronger when the rule of the mixture is applied because the pure alumina possesses approximately double Young's modulus than zirconia, 380 vs. 210 GPa, respectively. Therefore, the reactivity of both reinforcing phases with BCZT and detected reaction products substantially influenced the overall elastic behaviour.

The same trend was observed when indentation elastic modulus was obtained during the indentation hardness measurement (see Fig. 5b). Higher overall values above 120 GPa are the result of the used method because the effect of porosity was suppressed in the case of

indentation. Obtained values are on a similar level as reported for the indentation method [47]. The hardness HV0.3 of the alumina-reinforced BCZT increased above 5 GPa (1 vol.%), an increase of about 20%, but at higher concentrations decreased back to ~4.5 GPa, i.e., the level of the pure BCZT ceramics. The addition of zirconia led to a nearly linear microhardness increase up to 5.8 GPa (for 5 vol.%), approximately a 35% increase, which is above the expected value according to the rule of mixture taking into account the typical hardness of zirconia ~13 GPa. Moreover, the scatter was large, implying a higher degree of microstructural heterogeneity, i.e., distribution and size of reinforcing particles. The decrease in relative density should be disregarded because the indents affected by macroporosity were omitted; microporosity and/or secondary phases in the triple points could be the reason for the large hardness scatter.

Fig. 5 Dependence of a) elastic properties determined by IET and b) indentation hardness and modulus on reinforcing phase concentration.

The fracture behaviour of BCZT is similar to BaTiO₃. The measured fracture toughness value was at a level of 0.8 MPa·m^{1/2} [23], whilst alumina and zirconia usually reach higher values of ~3.5 MPa·m^{1/2} [48] and ~7.0 MPa·m^{1/2} [49], respectively. Therefore, the lowering of fracture toughness after adding 1 and 3 vol.% of zirconia (see Fig. 6) was probably caused by the joint effect of increasing porosity and dissolution of zirconia particles in the BCZT matrix. Zirconia particles can cause tensile stresses in the microstructure due to different coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE, 11.0·10⁻⁶ K⁻¹ [50] and 10.3·10⁻⁶ K⁻¹ [51] for BCZT and ZrO₂, respectively) and by introducing defects and disorder into the BCZT matrix. The addition of 5 vol.% of ZrO₂ resulted in higher fracture toughness but was accompanied by higher scatter, similar to indentation hardness. This could be caused by the saturated chemical reaction between BCZT and added ZrO₂.

The fracture toughness of the alumina-reinforced BCZT was slightly improved compared to the standard value of pure BCZT. This might be caused by the higher fracture toughness of alumina itself as well as of incidence of reaction products, namely spinel phase BaAl₂O₄. Aluminate spinels have been reported to have fracture toughness above 1.5 MPa·m^{1/2} [52–54]. A similar effect of Al₂O₃ on the fracture toughness of BaTiO₃ has been reported [29] and the increase has been attributed to crack bridging and crack closing by stress fields originating from secondary phases [55]. However, the CTE mismatch between phases (11.0·10⁻⁶ K⁻¹ [50] and 8·10⁻⁶ K⁻¹ [56] for BCZT and Al₂O₃, respectively) acted in opposition to the mentioned toughening mechanisms by generating tensile stresses in the matrix and compressive stresses in reinforcing particles [57]. The result of contradictory effects is a minimal fracture toughness increase above the pure BCZT standard. The fact that zirconia

particles are smaller than alumina ones indicated another reason for insufficient toughening by changing the trajectory of the main crack for smaller amounts of zirconia addition.

Fig. 6 Dependence of fracture toughness on reinforcing phases concentration.

The fracture surfaces shown in Fig. 7 are for 3% of alumina and zirconia contents and corresponding EDX maps show the distribution of Al and Zr elements within the fracture surface. In the case of alumina-reinforced BCZT, aluminium-containing particles formed an obstacle for the propagating crack and increased the fracture resistance. To easily identify aluminium-containing particles, an EDX map is shown. In general, the transgranular fracture mechanism was observed to predominate on the fracture surfaces of alumina-reinforced BCZT.

In the case of zirconia addition, the presence of Zr-rich particles on the fracture surface was not detected (see EDX map in Fig. 7) up to 3% of ZrO_2 ; at 5% of ZrO_2 some Zr spots were observed. The fracture surface also exhibited transgranular fracture, but a higher

amount of intergranular fracture was concentrated in the surrounding pores. This can be explained by the formation of the brittle phases at the grain boundaries connected to the pores. The particle addition influenced the fracture behaviour and the fracture toughness of the composites.

Fig. 7 Fracture surfaces of BCZT samples reinforced by 3 and 5 vol.% ZrO_2 and 3 vol.% Al_2O_3 .

3.5 Electrical properties

Dielectric properties

Fig. 8 shows the temperature-dependent relative permittivity (ϵ_r) for ZrO_2 and Al_2O_3 -reinforced BCZT in the temperature range from 30 to 120 °C (measured on poled samples during the heating cycle). For pure BCZT, the Curie temperature (T_C) was measured as 103.6 °C, and the maximum relative permittivity (ϵ_m) at T_C was measured as 9547. However, when the concentration of ZrO_2 was increased to 1 vol.%, the relative permittivities ϵ_r and ϵ_m started to decrease. Pure BCZT demonstrates orthorhombic-tetragonal (O-T) phase transition near room temperature, which can be also seen in small peak for Z1 or Z3. For higher Zr content, the Curie temperature decreases rapidly, and rhombohedral-orthorhombic (R-O) transition temperature increases towards T_C . Higher ϵ_r of the Z5 sample at the room temperature could be explained by the change in the composition and shift towards the relaxor behaviour, as discussed earlier.

The slope of the figure indicates a broadening of the peaks at the Curie temperature, suggesting a diffuse type phase transition [58]. These findings can be correlated with the XRD results, where an increased volume of ZrO_2 in the BCZT matrix resulted in a shift of the diffraction peaks to lower angles. This shift is attributed to the replacement of larger Ti^{4+} ions by smaller Zr^{4+} ions. BCZT reinforced with Al_2O_3 shows a similar behaviour, but to a lesser extent.

Fig. 8 Dependence of relative permittivity on temperature of a) ZrO_2 -reinforced BCZT and b) Al_2O_3 -reinforced BCZT.

At room temperature, there was approximately 3 times increase for zirconia-reinforced BCZT samples from 1741 (Z1) to 5166 (Z5) in ϵ_r values, while maintaining dielectric loss values ($\sim 2\%$) similar to that of pure BCZT counterpart (see Fig. 9, measured on unpoled samples). In contrast, the opposite effect was observed in the case of Al_2O_3 -reinforced ceramics showing a slightly decreasing ϵ_r and increasing dielectric loss trend.

Fig. 9 Dependence of a) relative permittivity ϵ_r and b) dielectric loss $\tan \delta$ on reinforcing phase concentration at room temperature (22 °C).

Piezoelectric properties

Fig. 10 shows the quasi-static piezoelectric constant (d_{33}) and planar coupling coefficients (k_p) for ZrO_2 -reinforced and Al_2O_3 -reinforced BCZT ceramics. The pure BCZT ceramics exhibited d_{33} and k_p values of approximately 395 pC/N and 50%, respectively, which are consistent with our previous findings [33,59]. However, an abrupt decrease in piezoelectric properties was observed as the ZrO_2 and Al_2O_3 contents increased. Specifically, the quasi-static d_{33} values decreased from 116 to 90 pC/N as the Al_2O_3 content increased from 1 to 5 vol.%. A similar effect was observed for the ZrO_2 -reinforced BCZT counterparts, with d_{33} values dropping from 280 to a mere 43 pC/N.

Fig. 10 Dependence of a) piezoelectric constant d_{33} and b) planar coupling coefficient k_p on reinforcing phase concentration.

Ferroelectric properties

Fig. 11 depicts the relationship between room temperature polarisation and electric field, while Fig. 12 illustrates displacement versus electric field, commonly known as butterfly

curves, for the reinforced BCZT ceramics. It is worth noting that all ceramics displayed well-defined hysteresis loops when measured at a frequency of 1 Hz and a maximum field of 3 kV/mm. The remnant polarisation (P_r) values exhibited a notable decrease from 8.1 to $0.86 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ for Zr-reinforced ceramics, whereas a slight decrease to $5.8 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ was observed for the Al-reinforced counterparts. The highest P_r and bipolar strain ($S_{bipolar}$) were demonstrated for pure BCZT as $8.1 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and $\sim 0.14\%$, respectively. This can be attributed to the elevated internal polarisability, strain, and electromechanical coupling, leading to an increased remnant polarisation [60]. Similar values of $S_{bipolar}$ were shown previously for pure BCZT [38].

Fig. 11 P-E hysteresis loops for a) ZrO_2 -reinforced BCZT and b) Al_2O_3 -reinforced BCZT.

Fig. 12 Strain hysteresis loops for a) ZrO_2 -reinforced BCZT and b) Al_2O_3 -reinforced BCZT.

It is interesting to note, that the ferroelectric properties decrease much faster with the reinforcing phase concentration for ZrO_2 than for Al_2O_3 -reinforced BCZT ceramic. Such behaviour must be related to the composition and properties of the interfaces between the particles (ZrO_2 or Al_2O_3) and the BCZT matrix. As mentioned above, new phases formed at the interfaces between the reinforcing particles and the BCZT matrix. Non-stoichiometric barium aluminate spinel (composition close to BaAl_2O_4) has previously been reported as a weak ferroelectric ($P_r \approx 0.01 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$) [61]. Therefore, the composites containing such a new phase may not lose as much ferroelectric polarisation compared to the particles without any ferroelectricity. Unfortunately, other new barium aluminate phases mentioned above and detected by XRD are not ferroelectric, so we can only speculate about their role in the ferroelectricity of composites.

The situation is different for ZrO_2 addition, as they are a natural part of the BCZT composition in the case of barium zirconate (BaZrO_3) or barium titanium zirconate BZT (especially $\text{Ba}(\text{Zr}_{0.2}\text{Ti}_{0.8})\text{O}_3$ composition or other Zr:Ti ratios), which developed at the

interfaces between BCZT matrix and particles. These compounds change the phase composition of the BCZT ceramics towards relaxor behaviour [62], which may change the ferroelectric properties substantially (T_C , dielectric, and piezoelectric properties). The ferroelectric properties of BZT ceramics are dependent on the Zr:Ti ratio, which exhibits P_r at values of $5 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ [63] and decrease the composite ferroelectric properties. Zirconia concentration of 5 vol.% evenly distributed over the composite volume is already high enough to influence most of the composite volume (i.e., one zirconia unit is surrounded by 26 closely packed neighbouring units of the same size in the composite, which means about 4 vol.% content).

The spontaneous polarisation values we measured for Al_2O_3 -reinforced BCZT composites are very similar to those previously reported by Yan et al. [21]. However, our ferroelectric data differ from those of Adhikari et al. [20] because they have used different processing conditions (e.g., lower sintering temperature) and their ceramics had a different phase composition (higher content of rhombohedral phase). No data has been reported so far for ZrO_2 -reinforced BCZT composites.

Adopting the calculation method (simple isostress-isostrain approximation keeping all quantities uniform within the matrix and reinforcing phases with possible discontinuities at the interfaces), we can derive formulae for the composite effective properties [64]. Permittivity is calculated as:

$$\varepsilon_{33}^{eff} = (v^{(2)})^{2/3} \frac{\varepsilon_{33}^{(1)} \varepsilon_{33}^{(2)}}{(1-v^{(2)})^{1/3} \varepsilon_{33}^{(2)} + (v^{(2)})^{1/3} \varepsilon_{33}^{(1)}} + \left(1 - (v^{(2)})^{2/3}\right) \varepsilon_{33}^{(1)},$$

piezoelectric coefficient could be expressed in combination of parallel and series averaging rules:

$$d_{33}^{eff} = \left\{ (v^{(2)})^{2/3} \varepsilon_{33}^{(1)} \frac{(1 - (v^{(2)})^{2/3}) d_{33}^{(1)} s_{33}^{(2)}}{(1 - (v^{(2)})^{2/3}) s_{33}^{(2)} + (v^{(2)})^{1/3} s_{33}^{(1)}} + \right. \\ \left. + (1 - (v^{(2)})^{1/3}) d_{33}^{(1)} \left[(1 - (v^{(2)})^{2/3}) \varepsilon_{33}^{(1)} + (v^{(2)})^{2/3} \varepsilon_{33}^{(2)} \right] \right\} / \\ / \left\{ (v^{(2)})^{1/3} \varepsilon_{33}^{(1)} + (1 - (v^{(2)})^{1/3}) \left[(1 - (v^{(2)})^{2/3}) \varepsilon_{33}^{(1)} + (v^{(2)})^{2/3} \varepsilon_{33}^{(2)} \right] \right\},$$

where superscripts ⁽¹⁾ and ⁽²⁾ are for the matrix and reinforcing phase, $d_{33}^{(1)}$ is piezoelectric coefficient for the matrix (reinforcing phases are not piezoelectric), $\varepsilon_{33}^{(1)}$, $\varepsilon_{33}^{(2)}$ are permittivities and $s_{33}^{(1)}$, $s_{33}^{(2)}$ elastic compliances for the matrix and reinforcing phase, $v^{(2)}$ is volume ratio of reinforcing phase. Values used for the numerical calculation are:

$\varepsilon_{33}^{(1)} = 1900$, $d_{33}^{(1)} = 395 \text{ pC/N}$, $s_{33}^{(1)} = 19.7 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ for BCZT, $\varepsilon_{33}^{(2)} = 10$, $s_{33}^{(2)} = 2.6 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ for Al_2O_3 , $\varepsilon_{33}^{(2)} = 20$, $s_{33}^{(2)} = 4.8 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ for ZrO_2 and $v^{(2)} = 0 \div 0.05$.

The dielectric, piezoelectric, and ferroelectric properties are listed in Table 3, which shows the comparison between experimental and calculated values. It can be seen that the experimental values of permittivity and especially piezoelectric coefficient decrease much faster than calculated by the combination of parallel and series averaging model. This could be due to the presence of reaction products not only at the grain boundaries but also within the grains and the increased porosity which further reduces the average properties.

Table 3 The dielectric, piezoelectric, and ferroelectric properties of composites (P_{max} is polarisation at 3 kV/mm).

Experiment							Theory	
Material	ϵ_r	d_{33}	P_r	P_{max}	E_c	T_C	ϵ_r	d_{33}
	[-]	[pC/N]	[$\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$]	[$\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$]	[V/mm]	[$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	[-]	[pC/N]
BCZT	1900	395	8.10	15.30	214	102	1900	395
A1	1570	116	7.40	15.20	220	95	1814	371
A3	1694	110	7.30	15.18	216	96	1720	337
A5	1437	90	5.80	12.80	202	94	1646	309
Z1	1741	280	8.00	14.70	209	96	1816	380
Z3	1578	130	5.12	11.10	276	81	1723	355
Z5	5166	43	0.86	8.24	85	32	1649	332

4 Conclusions

This work describes the effect of alumina or zirconia particles on the performance of lead-free BCZT piezoceramics. The reinforcing phases influenced the phase composition of the sintered samples; orthorhombic BCZT increased its proportion in the microstructure, and secondary phases were detected. A small amount of zirconia was retained in the microstructure, while alumina reacted completely to form BaAl_2O_4 , $\text{Ba}_6\text{Ti}_{17}\text{O}_{40}$ and $\text{Ba}_4\text{Ti}_{10}\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{27}$. The addition of zirconia slightly inhibited densification and grain growth, while alumina significantly refined the microstructure and, especially at low concentrations, improved the density. The elastic properties were enhanced by adding alumina particles up to 9% and zirconia particles up to 28%. Vickers hardness showed a similar trend with an increase of 20% and 35% above the values of BCZT for alumina and zirconia, respectively. The fracture behaviour characterised by fracture toughness was, from a statistical point of view, unchanged at the level of $0.8 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$. The reinforcement of the BCZT matrix by the zirconia and alumina particles decreased the dielectric, piezoelectric, and ferroelectric properties in both composite systems. However, the decrease was much smaller for similar volume content of alumina than for zirconia particles, which is due to a different mechanism of interfacial composition; resulting BaAl_2O_4 phase is weakly ferroelectric while added zirconia changed the BCZT phase composition substantially towards relaxor behaviour. The theoretical model of the dielectric and piezoelectric properties showed a much higher decrease, indicating the significant role of porosity in the composites.

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6 Data availability statement

The datasets generated and/or analysed during the current study are available in the repository, [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11380419>]

7 Conflict of interests

The authors have no competing interests to declare.

8 Figure captions

Fig. 1 XRD pattern (a), particle size distribution (b), and SEM micrograph (c) of calcined BCZT.

Fig. 2 X-ray diffraction patterns of sintered BCZT and BCZT reinforced by ZrO₂ (Z) or Al₂O₃ (A) ceramics and enlarged views of the peaks at $2\theta \approx 30^\circ$ and $2\theta \approx 45^\circ$.

Fig. 3 Dependence of relative density and MGS on the concentration of reinforcing Al₂O₃ and ZrO₂ ceramics in BCZT matrix.

Fig. 4 SEM micrographs of BCZT and BCZT with added 1, 3, 5 vol.% of ZrO₂ or Al₂O₃ and detailed micrographs of composite microstructure reinforced with 3 vol.% ZrO₂ or Al₂O₃ with highlighted spots for EDX spectra acquisition (note different scale bars).

Fig. 5 Dependence of a) elastic properties determined by IET and b) indentation hardness and modulus on reinforcing phase concentration.

Fig. 6 Dependence of fracture toughness on reinforcing phases concentration.

Fig. 7 Fracture surfaces of BCZT samples reinforced by 3 and 5 vol.% ZrO₂ and 3 vol.% Al₂O₃.

Fig. 8 Dependence of relative permittivity on temperature of a) ZrO₂-reinforced BCZT and b) Al₂O₃-reinforced BCZT.

Fig. 9 Dependence of a) relative permittivity ϵ_r and b) dielectric loss $\tan \delta$ on reinforcing phase concentration at room temperature (22 °C).

Fig. 10 Dependence of a) piezoelectric constant d_{33} and b) planar coupling coefficient k_p on reinforcing phase concentration.

Fig. 11 P-E hysteresis loops for a) ZrO₂-reinforced BCZT and b) Al₂O₃-reinforced BCZT.

Fig. 12 Strain hysteresis loops for a) ZrO₂-reinforced BCZT and b) Al₂O₃-reinforced BCZT.

9 References

- [1] B. Jaffe, W.R. Cook, H. Jaffe, *Piezoelectric Ceramics*, Academic Press, 1971.
- [2] K.W. Kwok, H.L.W. Chan, C.L. Choy, Comparison of the resonance characteristics of 1-3 composites of PZT in epoxy and PZT in P(VDF-TrFE) copolymer, *Ferroelectrics* 195 (1997) 119–122. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00150199708260501>.
- [3] E.El. Shafee, S.M. Behery, Preparation, characterisation and properties of novel 0–3 ferroelectric composites of $\text{Ba}_{0.95}\text{Ca}_{0.05}\text{Ti}_{0.8}\text{Zr}_{0.2}\text{O}_3$ –poly(vinylidene fluoride-trifluoroethylene), *Mater Chem Phys* 132 (2012) 740–746. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2011.12.005>.
- [4] A. Pelaiz-Barranco, R. Lopez-Noda, Dielectric relaxation and electrical conductivity in ferroelectric ceramic/polymer composite based on modified lead titanate, *J Appl Phys* 102 (2007). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2817609>.
- [5] S. V Glushanin, V.Y. Topolov, A hierarchy of inclusions and electromechanical properties of 0–3 ceramic/polymer composites, *J Phys D Appl Phys* 38 (2005) 2460–2467. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0022-3727/38/14/024>.
- [6] A. Pelaiz-Barranco, P. Marin-Franch, Piezo-, pyro-, ferro-, and dielectric properties of ceramic/polymer composites obtained from two modifications of lead titanate, *J Appl Phys* 97 (2005). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1847727>.
- [7] A. Seema, K.R. Dayas, J.M. Varghese, PVDF-PZT-5H composites prepared by hot press and tape casting techniques, *J Appl Polym Sci* 106 (2007) 146–151. <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.26673>.

- [8] Y. Bai, Z.-Y. Cheng, V. Bharti, H.S. Xu, Q.M. Zhang, High-dielectric-constant ceramic-powder polymer composites, *Appl Phys Lett* 76 (2000) 3804–3806.
<https://doi.org/10.1063/1.126787>.
- [9] I. Vrejoiu, J.D. Pedarnig, M. Dinescu, S. Bauer-Gogonea, D. Bäuerle, Flexible ceramic-polymer composite films with temperature-insensitive and tunable dielectric permittivity, *Appl Phys A Mater Sci Process* 74 (2002) 407–409.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s003390101137>.
- [10] D. Hennings, Barium titanate based ceramic materials for dielectric use, *International Journal of High Technology Ceramics* 3 (1987) 91–111.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0267-3762\(87\)90031-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0267-3762(87)90031-2).
- [11] O.P. Thakur, C. Prakash, A.R. James, Enhanced dielectric properties in modified barium titanate ceramics through improved processing, *J Alloys Compd* 470 (2009) 548–551. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2008.03.018>.
- [12] W. Liu, X. Ren, Large Piezoelectric Effect in Pb-Free Ceramics, *Phys Rev Lett* 103 (2009) 257602. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.103.257602>.
- [13] X. Liu, Z. Chen, B. Fang, J. Ding, X. Zhao, H. Xu, H. Luo, Enhancing piezoelectric properties of BCZT ceramics by Sr and Sn co-doping, *J Alloys Compd* 640 (2015) 128–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2015.04.029>.
- [14] J. Wu, D. Xiao, W. Wu, Q. Chen, J. Zhu, Z. Yang, J. Wang, Role of room-temperature phase transition in the electrical properties of (Ba, Ca)(Ti, Zr)O₃ ceramics, *Scr Mater* 65 (2011) 771–774.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2011.07.028>.

- [15] H.J. Hwang, M. Toriyama, T. Sekino, K. Niihara, In-situ fabrication of ceramic/Metal nanocomposites by reduction reaction in barium titanate–Metal oxide systems, *J Eur Ceram Soc* 18 (1998) 2193–2199. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0955-2219\(98\)00154-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0955-2219(98)00154-X).
- [16] H. Hyuga, Y. Hayashi, T. Sekino, K. Niihara, Fabrication process and electrical properties of BaTiO₃/Ni nanocomposites, *Nanostructured Materials* 9 (1997) 547–550. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0965-9773\(97\)00121-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0965-9773(97)00121-9).
- [17] C.Y. Chen, W.H. Tuan, Mechanical and Dielectric Properties of BaTiO₃/Ag Composites, *J Mater Sci Lett* 18 (1999) 353–354. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1006612129503>.
- [18] K. Tajima, H.J. Hwang, M. Sando, K. Niihara, PZT nanocomposites reinforced by small amount of oxides, *J Eur Ceram Soc* 19 (1999) 1179–1182. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0955-2219\(98\)00399-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0955-2219(98)00399-9).
- [19] S. Jiansirisomboon, A. Watcharapasorn, Effects of alumina nano-particulates addition on mechanical and electrical properties of barium titanate ceramics, *Curr Appl Phys* 8 (2008) 48–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cap.2007.04.008>.
- [20] P. Adhikari, R. Mazumder, G.K. Sahoo, Electrical and mechanical properties of 0.5Ba(Zr_{0.2}Ti_{0.8})O₃-0.5(Ba_{0.7}Ca_{0.3})TiO₃ (BZT-BCT) lead free ferroelectric ceramics reinforced with nano-sized Al₂O₃, *Ferroelectrics* 490 (2016) 60–69. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00150193.2015.1072013>.

- [21] X. Yan, M. Zheng, M. Zhu, Y. Hou, Enhanced electrical resistivity and mechanical properties in BCTZ-based composite ceramic, *J Adv Dielectr* 9 (2019).
<https://doi.org/10.1142/S2010135X1950036X>.
- [22] M. Mendelson, Average Grain Size in Polycrystalline Ceramics, *J Am Ceram Soc* 52 (1969) 443–446. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1151-2916.1969.tb11975.x>.
- [23] Z. Chlup, D. Drdlik, H. Hadraba, O. Sevecek, F. Siska, J. Erhart, K. Maca, Temperature effect on elastic and fracture behaviour of lead-free piezoceramic BaTiO₃, *J Eur Ceram Soc* 43 (2023) 1509–1522.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2022.11.030>.
- [24] J.I. Bluhm, Slice synthesis of a three dimensional “work of fracture” specimen, *Eng Fract Mech* 7 (1975) 593–604. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-7944\(75\)90059-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-7944(75)90059-4).
- [25] A. Di Loreto, R. Machado, A. Frattini, M.G. Stachiotti, Improvement in the sintering process of Ba_{0.85}Ca_{0.15}Zr_{0.1}Ti_{0.9}O₃ ceramics by the replacement of Zr by Hf, *J Mater Sci: Mater Electron* 28 (2017) 588–594. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10854-016-5562-6>.
- [26] P. Mishra, Sonia, P. Kumar, Effect of sintering temperature on dielectric, piezoelectric and ferroelectric properties of BZT-BCT 50/50 ceramics, *J Alloys Compd* 545 (2012) 210–215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2012.08.017>.
- [27] H. -Y Lu, J. -S Bow, W. -H Deng, Core-Shell Structures in ZrO₂-Modified BaTiO₃ Ceramic, *J Am Ceram Soc* 73 (1990) 3562–3568. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1151-2916.1990.tb04258.x>.

- [28] J.G. Fisher, B.K. Lee, S.Y. Choi, S.M. Wang, S.J.L. Kang, Inhibition of abnormal grain growth in BaTiO₃ by addition of Al₂O₃, *J Eur Ceram Soc* 26 (2006) 1619–1628. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2005.03.234>.
- [29] S. Jiansirisomboon, A. Watcharapasorn, T. Tunkasiri, Fabrication, Microstructure and Mechanical Properties Relations of Ferroelectric Barium Titanate Reinforced with Alumina Micro/Nano Particulates, in: 11th International Ceramics Congress, Trans Tech Publications Ltd, 2006: pp. 2406–2411. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/ast.45.2406>.
- [30] S. Jayanthi, T.R.N. Kutty, Effect of segregative additives on the positive temperature coefficient in resistance characteristics of n-BaTiO₃ ceramics, *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics* 17 (2006) 883–897. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10854-006-0038-8>.
- [31] Y. Bai, A. Matousek, P. Tofel, V. Bijalwan, B. Nan, H. Hughes, T.W. Button, (Ba,Ca)(Zr,Ti)O₃ lead-free piezoelectric ceramics-The critical role of processing on properties, *J Eur Ceram Soc* 35 (2015) 3445–3456. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2015.05.010>.
- [32] N. Buatip, M. Dhanunjaya, P. Amonpattaratkit, P. Pomyai, T. Sonklin, K. Reichmann, P. Janphaung, S. Pojprapai, Comparison of conventional and reactive sintering techniques for Lead-Free BCZT ferroelectric ceramics, *Radiation Physics and Chemistry* 172 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radphyschem.2020.108770>.

- [33] V. Bijalwan, P. Tofel, J. Erhart, K. Maca, The complex evaluation of functional properties of nearly dense BCZT ceramics and their dependence on the grain size, *Ceram Int* 45 (2019) 317–326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2018.09.169>.
- [34] V. Bijalwan, I. Sokolov, P. Tofel, Poling procedures and piezoelectric response of $(\text{Ba}_{0.85}\text{Ca}_{0.15}\text{Zr}_{0.1}\text{Ti}_{0.9})\text{O}_3$ ceramics, *J Asian Ceram Soc* 9 (2021) 206–213. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21870764.2020.1860438>.
- [35] V. Bijalwan, V. Prajzler, J. Erhart, H. Tan, P. Roupčova, D. Sobola, P. Tofel, K. Maca, Rapid pressure-less and spark plasma sintering of $(\text{Ba}_{0.85}\text{Ca}_{0.15}\text{Zr}_{0.1}\text{Ti}_{0.9})\text{O}_3$ lead-free piezoelectric ceramics, *J Eur Ceram Soc* 41 (2021) 2514–2523. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2020.11.029>.
- [36] R.D. Shannon, Revised effective ionic radii and systematic studies of interatomic distances in halides and chalcogenides, *Acta Crystallographica Section A* 32 (1976) 751–767. <https://doi.org/10.1107/S0567739476001551>.
- [37] Q. Xu, Z. Li, Dielectric and ferroelectric behaviour of Zr-doped BaTiO_3 perovskites, *Processing and Application of Ceramics* 14 (2020) 188–194. <https://doi.org/10.2298/pac2003188x>.
- [38] V. Bijalwan, J. Erhart, Z. Spatz, D. Sobola, V. Prajzler, P. Tofel, K. Maca, Composition driven $(\text{Ba,Ca})(\text{Zr,Ti})\text{O}_3$ lead-free ceramics with large quality factor and energy harvesting characteristics, *J Am Ceram Soc* 104 (2021) 1088–1101. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jace.17497>.
- [39] R. Hayati, M.A. Bahrevar, T. Ebadzadeh, V. Rojas, N. Novak, J. Koruza, Effects of Bi_2O_3 additive on sintering process and dielectric, ferroelectric, and piezoelectric

- properties of $(\text{Ba}_{0.85}\text{Ca}_{0.15})(\text{Zr}_{0.1}\text{Ti}_{0.9})\text{O}_3$ lead-free piezoceramics, *J Eur Ceram Soc* 36 (2016) 3391–3400. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2016.05.033>.
- [40] J. Hao, W. Bai, W. Li, J. Zhai, Correlation Between the Microstructure and Electrical Properties in High-Performance $(\text{Ba}_{0.85}\text{Ca}_{0.15})(\text{Zr}_{0.1}\text{Ti}_{0.9})\text{O}_3$ Lead-Free Piezoelectric Ceramics, *Journal of the American Ceramic Society* 95 (2012) 1998–2006. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1551-2916.2012.05146.x>.
- [41] P. Bharathi, K.B.R. Varma, Grain and the concomitant ferroelectric domain size dependent physical properties of $(\text{Ba}_{0.85}\text{Ca}_{0.15}\text{Zr}_{0.1}\text{Ti}_{0.9})\text{O}_3$ ceramics fabricated using powders derived from oxalate precursor route, *J Appl Phys* 116 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4900494>.
- [42] D. Drdlik, D. Zeman, P. Tofel, Z. Chlup, H. Hadraba, K. Drdlikova, A comparative study of direct and indirect evaluation of piezoelectric properties of electrophoretically deposited (Ba, Ca) (Zr, Ti) O_3 lead-free piezoceramics, *Ceram Int* 47 (2021) 2034–2042. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2020.09.035>.
- [43] N. Moelans, B. Blanpain, P. Wollants, Phase field simulations of grain growth in two-dimensional systems containing finely dispersed second-phase particles, *Acta Mater* 54 (2006) 1175–1184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2005.10.045>.
- [44] V. Bijalwan, P. Tofel, V. Holcman, Grain size dependence of the microstructures and functional properties of $(\text{Ba}_{0.85}\text{Ca}_{0.15-x}\text{Ce}_x)(\text{Zr}_{0.1}\text{Ti}_{0.9})\text{O}_3$ lead-free piezoelectric ceramics, *J Asian Ceram Soc* 6 (2018) 384–393. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21870764.2018.1539211>.

- [45] V. Bijalwan, P. Tofel, Synthesis of high density sub-10 μm $(\text{Ba}_{0.85}\text{Ca}_{0.15})(\text{Zr}_{0.1}\text{Ti}_{0.9})\text{O}_{3-x}\text{CeO}_2$ lead-free ceramics using a two-step sintering technique, *J Asian Ceram Soc* 7 (2019) 536–543.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/21870764.2019.1683954>.
- [46] D. Kollner, S. Simon, S. Niedermeyer, I. Spath, E. Wolf, K. Kakimoto, T. Fey, Relation between Structure, Mechanical and Piezoelectric Properties in Cellular Ceramic Auxetic and Honeycomb Structures, *Adv Eng Mater* 25 (2023).
<https://doi.org/10.1002/adem.202201387>.
- [47] I. Coondoo, N. Panwar, D. Alikin, I. Bdikin, S.S. Islam, A. Turygin, V.Y. Shur, A.L. Kholkin, A comparative study of structural and electrical properties in lead-free BCZT ceramics: Influence of the synthesis method, *Acta Mater* 155 (2018) 331–342.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2018.05.029>.
- [48] J. Kubler, Fracture Toughness of Ceramics Using the SEVNB Method a Joint VAMSA/ESIS Round Robin, in: *Fracture Mechanics of Ceramics*, Springer US, Boston, MA, 2002: pp. 437–445. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4757-4019-6_33.
- [49] M. Trunec, Z. Chlup, Higher fracture toughness of tetragonal zirconia ceramics through nanocrystalline structure, *Scr Mater* 61 (2009) 56–59.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2009.03.019>.
- [50] Y. He, Heat capacity, thermal conductivity, and thermal expansion of barium titanate-based ceramics, *Thermochim Acta* 419 (2004) 135–141.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tca.2004.02.008>.

- [51] H. Hayashi, T. Saitou, N. Maruyama, H. Inaba, K. Kawamura, M. Mori, Thermal expansion coefficient of yttria stabilised zirconia for various yttria contents, *Solid State Ion* 176 (2005) 613–619. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssi.2004.08.021>.
- [52] A. Ghosh, K.W. White, M.G. Jenkins, A.S. Kobayashi, R.C. Brad, Fracture Resistance of a Transparent Magnesium Aluminate Spinel, *J Am Ceram Soc* 74 (1991) 1624–1630. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1151-2916.1991.tb07149.x>.
- [53] A.F. Dericioglu, A.R. Boccaccini, I. Dlouhy, Y. Kagawa, Effect of Chemical Composition on the Optical Properties and Fracture Toughness of Transparent Magnesium Aluminate Spinel Ceramics, *Mater Trans* 46 (2005) 996–1003. <https://doi.org/10.2320/matertrans.46.996>.
- [54] C.B. Huang, T.C. Lu, L. Bin Lin, M.Y. Lei, C.X. Huang, A Study on Toughening and Strengthening of Mg-Al Spinel Transparent Ceramics, *Key Eng Mater* 336–338 (2007) 1207–1210. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/kem.336-338.1207>.
- [55] P.F. Becher, Microstructural Design of Toughened Ceramics, *J Am Ceram Soc* 74 (1991) 255–269. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1151-2916.1991.tb06872.x>.
- [56] D. Kuscer, I. Bantan, M. Hrovat, B. Malic, The microstructure, coefficient of thermal expansion and flexural strength of cordierite ceramics prepared from alumina with different particle sizes, *J Eur Ceram Soc* 37 (2017) 739–746. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2016.08.032>.
- [57] Z. Chlup, H. Hadraba, D. Drdlik, K. Maca, I. Dlouhy, R. Bermejo, On the determination of the stress-free temperature for alumina–zirconia multilayer

structures, *Ceram Int* 40 (2014) 5787–5793.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2013.11.018>.

- [58] H. Baloria, D. Nanda, S. Thakur, R. Rai, A. Singh, Structural, dielectric and impedance response of BCT reinforcement on BZT matrix, *J Mater Sci: Mater Electron* 32 (2021) 19688–19702. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10854-021-06491-4>.
- [59] V. Bijalwan, V. Prajzler, J. Erhart, J.J. Velazquez, D. Galusek, K. Maca, Rapid pressureless sintering of barium titanate-based piezoceramics and their electromechanical harvesting performance, *J Am Ceram Soc* 105 (2022) 6886–6897. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jace.18602>.
- [60] G.H. Haertling, *Ferroelectric Ceramics: History and Technology*, *J Am Ceram Soc* 82 (1999) 797–818. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1151-2916.1999.tb01840.x>.
- [61] S.-Y. Huang, R. Von Der Muhll, J. Ravez, P. Hagemuller, Structural, ferroelectric and pyroelectric properties of nonstoichiometric ceramics based on BaAl_2O_4 , *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids* 55 (1994) 119–124. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3697\(94\)90192-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3697(94)90192-9).
- [62] M. Acosta, N. Novak, V. Rojas, S. Patel, R. Vaish, J. Koruza, G.A. Rossetti, J. Rodel, BaTiO_3 -based piezoelectrics: Fundamentals, current status, and perspectives, *Appl Phys Rev* 4 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4990046>.
- [63] F. Moura, A.Z. Simoes, B.D. Stojanovic, M.A. Zaghete, E. Longo, J.A. Varela, Dielectric and ferroelectric characteristics of barium zirconate titanate ceramics prepared from mixed oxide method, *J Alloys Compd* 462 (2008) 129–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2007.07.077>.

- [64] W. Pabst, S. Hribalova, T. Uhlírova, Quasi-laminate and quasi-columnate modeling of dielectric and piezoelectric properties of cubic-cell metamaterials, *J Eur Ceram Soc* 42 (2022) 1396–1406. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2021.12.013>.